

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

D1.1 Project Handbook

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Horizon Innovation action

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Abstract

The ECHOES Project Handbook brings together the core principles and practical guidelines that shape how the consortium works together. It sets out how the project is managed, how partners report progress, and how they communicate and disseminate. It also outlines how innovation is handled and how results are shared and protected. This handbook is designed to support smooth collaboration and ensure everyone is aligned throughout the project's duration.

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Introduction

The project handbook offers guidelines for ECHOES partners. It covers the most important aspects of the project, including the management structure, project reporting, working methods, innovation management, intellectual property and data protection. This handbook provides complementary, practical information for partners to implement the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA) regarding governance, project management, monitoring, approval of deliverables, communication and any other administrative issues.

The Handbook is organised in the following sections:

Section 1 - Project Management Structures

Section 2 - Project Reporting

Section 3 - Working methods

Section 4 - Innovation Management and Intellectual Property

Section 5 - Data protection

Section 1 – Project management structure

1. Roles and responsibilities

The project is organised in different Consortium Bodies which all have a specific function to facilitate the technical work and organisation. The ECHOES governance structure is illustrated by the following scheme:

Figure 1 ECHOES governance

Each Consortium Body has specific responsibilities, which are listed below. All partners are members of the General Assembly, consisting of one representative per beneficiary.

CONSORTIUM		
Consortium body	Role and responsibilities	Member(s)
Coordinator	<p>The intermediary between the Parties and the European Commission.</p> <p>Chair of all the meetings of the General Assembly and the Steering Committee,</p> <p>Overall technical implementation and management,</p> <p>Provides, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims</p> <p>Collects information for the termination report in case of termination of a Party's participation.</p> <p><u>Reports to the Steering Committee, the General Assembly and the European Commission.</u></p>	Xavier RODIER (CNRS)
Executive Board (EB)	<p>Operational body.</p> <p>Assists and facilitates the work of the Coordinator in the execution of the General Assembly decisions,</p> <p>Assist the preparation of Steering Committee and other Consortium Bodies meetings.</p> <p><u>Reports to the Coordinator.</u></p>	<p>Chaired by Emanuel DEMETRESCU (CNR)</p> <p>Representatives from the CNRS</p> <p>Representatives from the CNR and the FSP</p>
Steering Committee (SC)	<p>Supervisory body for the execution of the Project.</p> <p>Prepares the meetings, proposes decisions and prepares the agenda of the General Assembly,</p>	Chaired by the Coordinator, Xavier RODIER (CNRS),

	<p>Pursues a consensus among the Parties,</p> <p>Assesses deliverables and milestones being in line with scheduled work plan and prepare the periodic reporting for the work packages together with the Coordinator.</p> <p><u>Reports to the General Assembly.</u></p>	<p>Pillar coordinators: Isabelle PALLOT-FROSSARD (FSP): Communities, Dimitris KOTZINOS (CNRS-CYU): Knowledge, Paolo CIGNONI (CNR): Innovation, Xavier RODIER (CNRS): Sustainability,</p> <p>WP leaders,</p> <p>Executive Board chairperson (permanent observer).</p>
General Assembly (GA)	<p>Highest decision-making body.</p> <p>Decides on:</p> <p>Finances and intellectual property rights,</p> <p>The evolution of the Consortium (partners entering/leaving),</p> <p>Defaulting party status and litigation, breach,</p> <p>Appointments of the Scientific Committee members and Technical Assessment Council members.</p> <p><u>Final decision-making body.</u></p>	<p>Chair: Xavier RODIER (CNRS), Coordinator,</p> <p>One representative by Beneficiary (list: see Annex I),</p> <p>Representatives of Associated Partners (permanent observers),</p> <p>Representatives of ECCCH project leaders (permanent observers).</p>
Work Package leaders	<p>Coordinate the completion of activities for the tasks in the relevant Work package.</p>	<p>WP1: Xavier RODIER (CNRS)</p> <p>WP2: Franco NICCOLUCCI (ARIADNE)</p> <p>WP3: Sally CHAMBERS (DARIAH)</p> <p>WP4: Rémi PETITCOL (FSP)</p> <p>WP5: Julia FALLON/Ad Pollé (Europeana)</p> <p>WP6: Aleksandra NOWAK (PSNC)</p>

		<p>WP7: Sorin HERMON (CyI)</p> <p>WP8: Paolo CIGNONI (CNR)</p> <p>WP9: Carlos ANDUJAR (UPC)</p> <p>WP10: Philippe VENDRIX (CNRS)</p> <p>WP11: Vania VIRGILI (CNR)</p> <p>WP12: Dimitris KOTZINOS (CY)</p>
ECHOES Integration Task Force (EITF)	<p>Plan and monitor the selection and integration of datasets, tools and workflows into the ECHOES Platform,</p> <p>Provide a basis for developing the Collaborative Research Scenarios that will focus on re-using resources,</p> <p>Undertake user testing as part of the continuous assessment of ECHOES tools and services.</p>	<p>WP4 to WP8 leaders,</p> <p>ECCCH Project leaders.</p>
INDEPENDENT AND EXTERNAL BOARDS		
Board	Role and responsibilities	Member(s)
Policy Advisory Board (PAB)	<p>Ensure coherence at the policy level between all ECCCH-related activities.</p> <p>It elects a Chair on its first meetings and is responsible for its own rules of procedures, including the addition of new members</p> <p>Benefits from the operational support of the Executive Board,</p> <p>Provides recommendations on strategic decisions related to governance and sustainability of the Cloud within its ecosystem.</p>	<p>Initial list suggested by the SC and elected by the GA. This board can have the maximum of 20 members, to be included along the duration of the project.</p> <p>Manuel CASTIÑEIRAS GONZALEZ (ES)</p> <p>Chris DE LOOF (BE)</p> <p>David DE ROURE (UK)</p> <p>David FIALA (FR)</p>

		<p>Pascal LIEVAUX (FR)</p> <p>Paul KELLER (NE)</p> <p>Marina SOLOMIDOU-IERONYMIDOU (CY)</p> <p>Eva STENSKÖLD (SE)</p> <p>Elena THEODOULOU-CHARALAMBOUS (CY)</p> <p>Brigitte VEZINA (NE)</p> <p>Ben WAGNER (NE)</p> <p>Katarzyna WALETKO (PL)</p>
<p>Scientific Committee (ScC)</p>	<p>It will assess the Cloud's structure and evolving components, tools and services.</p> <p>It elects a Chair on its first meetings and is responsible for its own rules of procedures, including the addition of new members,</p> <p>Provides expert advice to activities carried out within ECHOES,</p> <p>Provides expert advice on activities performed in other ECCCH funded projects,</p> <p>Share the minutes with the General Assembly.</p>	<p>It is currently composed of 13 experts suggested by the SC and elected by the GA.</p> <p>Pere BRUNET (ES)</p> <p>Livio DE LUCA (FR)</p> <p>Paola DERUDAS (SE)</p> <p>Diane DUSSEAUX (FR)</p> <p>Eero HYVÖNEN (FI)</p> <p>Adeline JOFFRES (FR)</p> <p>Peter PLASSMEYER (DE)</p> <p>Martjn PRONK (NE)</p> <p>Antonino ROTOLO (NE)</p> <p>Roberto SCOPIGNO (IT)</p> <p>Matija STRLIC (SI)</p> <p>Melissa TERRAS (UK)</p>

		Jean François TRUBERT (FR)
Technical Assessment Committee (TAC)	<p>It will assess the Cloud's structure and the evolving components, tools and services. Once established, it will be linked to the legal entity.</p> <p>It elects a Chair on its first meetings and is responsible for its own rules of procedures, including the addition of new members,</p> <p>Provides expert advice to the technical activities carried out within ECHOES,</p> <p>Sends the minutes to the General Assembly</p>	<p>It is currently composed of 8 experts from the computer sciences domain and from different sectors of CH.</p> <p>CANDELO Gustavo (ES)</p> <p>GUELTON Rémi (FR)</p> <p>JONES Bob (CH)</p> <p>LESJAK Dejan (SI)</p> <p>LEVERS Andrew (UK)</p> <p>NEGRI Antonella (IT)</p> <p>SZPROT Jakub (PO)</p> <p>VAN WEZEL Jos (DE)</p>
Stakeholders Council (Stac)	<p>Will organise other ECCCH-funded projects and Representatives from other European initiatives related to CH.</p> <p>It elects a Chair on its first meetings and is responsible for its own rules of procedures, including the addition of new members,</p> <p>Sends the minutes to the General Assembly,</p> <p>Advises the General Assembly.</p>	<p>Final list expected by Autumn 2025</p> <p>ECCCH-funded projects ;</p> <p>Representatives from other European initiatives related to CH.</p>

Table 1: Roles and responsibilities in the Consortium

2. Meetings

All bodies of the consortium meet regularly to discuss and assess the progress and share information and results. Any party should have one representative in a meeting and participate in a cooperative manner.

For the General Assembly, the agenda must be sent 21 calendar days in advance for ordinary meetings, 10 calendar days in advance for an extraordinary meeting. For the Steering Committee, it is 7 calendar days in advance for ordinary and extraordinary meetings.

The agenda, the minutes and the attendance list must be provided by the Chair of the meeting.

Board	Ordinary meetings	Extraordinary meetings
Executive board	Once a month, the first Friday of the month.	NES
Steering Committee	Quarterly	Upon request of any member of the SC Notice: 7 calendar days before.
General Assembly	Once a year	Upon request of the SC or 1/3 of the GA Notice: 15 calendar days before.
ECHOES Integration Task Force	Quarterly	NES
Scientific Committee	Once a year, remote or in person, usually during an ECHOES Annual event	Upon request of the SC or 1/3 of the GA Notice: 15 calendar days before.
Policy Advisory Board	Once a year, remote or in person, usually during an ECHOES Annual event	Upon request of the SC or 1/3 of the GA Notice: 15 calendar days before.
Technical Assessment Committee	Once a year, remote or in person	To be decided at its first meeting
Stakeholders Council	Once a year, remote or in person	Once a year, remote or in person

Table 2. ECHOES Management Board meetings schedule

3. Decision-making

The Parties agree to respect all decisions of the General Assembly. Each Party has one vote.

A decision may also be taken without a meeting. More details about this procedure are available on the Grant Agreement on the section 6.3.1.3 for the General Assembly and the section 6.3.2.4 for the Steering Committee.

Section 2 – Project reporting

Within the project, three forms of reporting have to be distinguished: internal reporting, continuous reporting, and periodic reporting.

1. Internal reporting

Within the project, a system of internal reporting has been implemented in order for the Coordinator, the Steering Committee and the Executive Board to keep track of the activities of each partner and each Work Package.

Once every quarter (three months), the beneficiaries must fill in a report outlining the activities their teams carried out for each WP. They must describe the actions undertaken in the relevant WPs, the person/month devoted to the project during the quarter, and, if applicable, the trips and mobilities that their work for ECHOES entailed.

A similar report is required of each WP leader at the same frequency, and must recount the actions that were planned for the time period in the Grant Agreement, and the actions that were actually implemented. If there are any differences between the two, the WP leader must explain the reasons (difficulties encountered, miscalculated time, etc.).

A template is provided to each beneficiary and each WP leader for this exercise, and the reports must be uploaded onto MS Teams or sent to the coordination team. The following folder is dedicated to the progress reports. The templates and all progress reports will be uploaded in the files corresponding to the appropriate reporting periods: Internal progress reports.

These documents, also called 'progress reports', are purely internal to the project, and are not meant to be uploaded onto the Funding and Tenders platform. Instead, they are an efficient method of record-keeping, and a way for the Coordinator and their team to have a regular overview of the work that has been done, and to be informed if there are any delays or issues with certain tasks or Work Packages.

2. Continuous reporting

The term ‘continuous reporting’ in the context of this project refers to the account of the beneficiaries’ advancement given to the European Commission by means of the deliverables, milestones, etc. It is, in reality, the proof that we, as partners, are making progress in the development and implementation of our activities.

The calendar of the continuous reporting was agreed upon by the granting authority (the European Research Executive Agency – REA) and the ECHOES partners, as beneficiaries of the grant, must keep up with it.

a. Deliverables

Deliverables are defined as “Outputs to be submitted to the EU (publication, leaflet, progress report, brochure, list, etc.)” on the European Commission’s Funding and Tenders platform.

A timeline of project deliverables can be found in the Grant Agreement on pages 45-50, Annex 1, Part A. The table is followed by a more detailed description of the content of each deliverable (p.51-66).

As a matter of fact, for any given deliverable, the Grant Agreement provides the following information:

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
D1.1	Project Handbook (WP1)	WP1	1 - CNRS	R — Document, report	PU - Public	4
Description						8
Procedures for project quality assurance, project implementation performance (KPIs) internal communication, template for reporting, monitoring, approval of deliverables.						

1: The number of the deliverable, composed of the number of the Work Package it relates to, and a number corresponding to its position in the list of deliverables due for this WP,

2: The name/title of the deliverable,

3: The WP it is linked to, and whose responsibility it is to produce the deliverable,

4: The Lead Beneficiary, meaning the partner who must oversee the preparation of the deliverable,

5: The type of document – most often a deliverable is a written report, but it may take other forms, such as a Data Management Plan (D1.2) or a prototype (D8.2 for example),

6: The Dissemination level, which indicates the level of confidentiality (Public, Sensitive or EU Classified) of the deliverable and thus may limit how or to whom the deliverable can be shared,

7: The due date, corresponding to a given month in the project, meaning the deliverable must be uploaded on the online platform by the last day of this month (for example, month 4 of the project is September 2024, so the deliverable is due for 30 Sept. 2024).

8: And finally, a short description of the deliverable to guide the partners in its production.

In addition to the information given in the Grant Agreement, an internal deliverable review procedure have been devised by the partners in order to manage their production as effectively as possible:

Date	Task to be carried out
One month before the deadline	The Coordinator sends an email reminding the work package leader of the deadline of the deliverable.
Two weeks before the deadline	The WP leader sends the latest version of the deliverable to the Coordinator
One week before the deadline	The Coordinator provides the WP leader with a critical review and suggests changes to the content and form of the deliverable by adding comments to the shared document.
Three days before the deadline	The WP leader finalises the deliverable.
One to two days before the deadline	After final validation from the Coordinator and WP leader, the Coordinator submits the deliverable to the online platform.

Table 3. Internal deliverable review procedure

If ever the partners realise that they are late in the production of a deliverable, and that it will most likely not be uploaded on the platform on time, it is crucial they inform the Coordinator, who is in charge of advising the Project Officer of the delay.

b. Milestones

Milestones are defined by the European Commission's Funding and Tenders platform as "Control points in the project that help to chart progress (kick-off meetings, steering committees, first-draft of a survey, prototype, etc.) They may correspond to the completion of a key deliverable, which allows the next phase of the work to begin or is needed at intermediary points."

A table of the project's milestones can be found in the Grant agreement on pages 67-69, Annex 1, Part A. Similarly, to the deliverables list, the milestones list provides the following information:

Milestone No 1	Milestone Name 2	Work Package No 3	Lead Beneficiary 4	Means of Verification 5	Due Date (month) 6
1	Kick Off Meeting	WP4, WP5, WP3, WP1, WP2, WP8, WP9, WP11, WP7, WP6, WP10, WP12	1 - CNRS	Minutes of the kick-off meeting.	2

1: The number of the milestone, in order of the due dates,

2: The name of the milestone,

3: The WP(s) it relates to,

4: The Lead beneficiary, meaning the partner responsible for ensuring that the milestone is achieved,

5: The means of verification of the achievement of the milestone, meaning the tangible evidence of the achievement of the milestone to provide as proof of advancement,

6: The due date, corresponding to a month of the project and meaning that the milestone should be achieved by the last day of the given month.

c. Other means of continuous reporting

Although deliverables and milestones are the most tangible kind of evidence for the advancement of the project, the reporting to the European Commission can take other forms:

- An account of the mitigation measures and responses provided to the critical risks encountered during the implementation of the project can be provided on the online platform.
- Updating the project summary on the platform is also an appropriate way to show progress: as it is made for publication, providing more detail and better defining the objectives and activities of the partners in the summary demonstrates the progress made on the project.
- A list of dissemination and communication activities can also be uploaded to the online platform to show how the partners on the project are reaching out to the relevant communities.

The ECHOES Teams will allow the partners to keep track of such advancements, and the Coordination team will update the platform regularly. Any information relevant to the continuous reporting can be uploaded in the 'Continuous reporting' file: [Continuous reporting](#). Updating the platform regularly will ease the periodic reporting process.

3. Periodic reporting

In addition to uploading the deliverables, milestones and other advancements on the platform once they are completed, the project partners must also periodically craft a general report their progress.

The following table, outlining the reporting periods, can be found in the Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement:

Reporting					Payments	
Reporting periods			Type	Deadline	Type	Deadline (time to pay)
RP No	Month from	Month to				
					Initial prefinancing	30 days from entry into force/10 days before starting date – whichever is the latest
1	1	24	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
2	25	48	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
3	49	60	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Final payment	90 days from receiving periodic report

As indicated by the table above, after the initial prefinancing, there are three reporting periods:

- The first, running from the start of the project to the two-year mark,
- The second, from the beginning of the third year to the end of the fourth,
- And the third, spanning over the fifth and final year of the project.

After the end of a reporting period, the beneficiaries have sixty days to upload all the information required in the periodic report to the Funding and Tenders platform.

A periodic report is composed of two parts: a technical report, and a financial report.

a. The technical report

The technical report contains, first, an account of the continual reporting carried out by the partners (Part A). It gathers information about all the activities of the period: the deliverables handed in, the milestones achieved, the critical risks encountered and the methods used to mitigate them, as well as the events, the communication and dissemination activities, the Key Points of Interest (KPIs), and any other type of result obtained or impact observed during the period.

Most of the tabs shown above are completed by the continual reporting – especially if the partners have regularly updated their progress – but it is important that, at the end of the reporting period, each partner makes sure that all relevant information has been communicated so the final report is complete.

Of this information is derived the status of the Work Packages, meaning their level of advancement. It is important to note that the progress of a WP is based on the activities carried out, and not on the results obtained: a WP can be considered as completed even though the objectives have not been reached if activities – whether they were planned in the proposal or not – have been implemented to reach them. If a WP is not completed by the announced deadline, it can be completed in a subsequent reporting period. Moreover, at the time of the final reporting period, if a Work Package is not fully completed, a percentage of completion is nevertheless indicated, and will correspond to the payment made in consequence.

The technical report also contains a narrative part (Part B), which gives a more detailed explanation of the work carried out. It takes the form of a PDF document that follows the template of the platform, to be uploaded only for the purpose of the periodic report.

When the end of a reporting period is upcoming, the Coordination team will send a reminder email to all partners and invite them to meet with the leaders of the WPs they are involved in to take stock of the work done over the period. Once the activities have been reported and the narrative part has been crafted, the Coordinator will collect this information and upload it onto the platform.

b. The financial report

This part of the periodic report indicates how the sums previously received have been used.

A financial statement is generated by the platform for the Coordinator, and contains the financial information for all the beneficiaries. It takes the following form:

FINANCIAL STATEMENT FOR THE ACTION FOR REPORTING PERIOD (NUMBER)												
No contribution												Requested for contribution
By/In kind contributions (per work package)												
WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	WP1 (name)	
Period of funding	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)	Contribution (WP1) (name) (Reporting not needed for costs)
Period of completion	COMPLETED	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	PARTIALLY COMPLETED	COMPLETED	NOT COMPLETED							
	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
1- (short name beneficiary)												
1.1- (short name affiliated entity)												
2- (short name beneficiary)												
2.1- (short name affiliated entity)												
3- (short name associated partner)												
Total contribution												

It is derived from the status of the Work Packages, thus, if it needs to be corrected, it is necessary that the status of WPs is modified first. Once the financial statement is correct, the Coordinator signs it off, guaranteeing that the information it contains is exact.

Section 3 – Working methods

It is essential to develop working methods that facilitate communication and file sharing between all the partners involved, particularly in view of the large consortium involved in the ECHOES project.

The communication tools and working methods introduced in the following sections altogether will contribute to a working environment in which project members can collaborate and work in a most efficient way.

1. Internal communication and tools

Communication within the project will happen through different channels of work packages.

Whilst face-to-face meetings will be held on a regular basis, yet with a rather low frequency, ECHOES members, including advisory bodies and WP teams, will communicate on a daily basis in Microsoft Teams.

All internal communication will therefore be carried out primarily through this tool, as well as by email for the organisation of important events or urgent reminders about deliverables, for example.

In order to facilitate communication between the various partners in the consortium, a contact masterlist with everyone's email address has been created and uploaded to the TEAMS group: <https://teams.microsoft.com/l/team/19%3AbIbWg3vxa1vtxEKDghp8YwIdGd4tz8w1MGuYjrsFAMg1%40thread.tacv2/conversations?groupId=4127ba4d-09e3-40ad-856b-27257610b49f&tenantId=16150599-ebb0-4fcf-94a5-6010823c7bd5>

a. Communication platform

The project management software Microsoft Teams used in the ECHOES project brings together multiple hubs of communication. It is a workspace for real-time collaboration and communication, meetings, file and app sharing (see below).

Microsoft Teams will allow all project team members to communicate and collaborate on all ECHOES tasks via channels.

Recognised as an effective collaboration tool for project management, the Teams platform enables partners to have private conversations and create groups with many participants, via real-time messaging, start, follow or contribute to discussions on the discussion platform, share documents and link documents saved in Documents.

As well as the overall project environment, there are also team environments for each work package. All project members have access to all teams and documents, unless specifically restricted. New project members should contact the ECHOES project manager to obtain an invitation to join the ECHOES group on Teams.

The guidelines below relate to the ECHOES customized set-up in Microsoft Teams:

1. Channels have been created for each WP and other relevant categories in the General channel, such as Event, Official documents, etc. Each project team member should be added to the team(s) on which they will be working and will automatically be added to the teams relevant to the entire consortium.
2. Each channel contains the 'Posts' and 'Files' tabs.
 - 'Posts' should be used for communication related to the channel's topic.
 - 'Files' gives access to the SharePoint folder (and sub-folders) connected to the individual channel.
3. Each Work Package channel has three separate folders:
 - Deliverables
 - Reporting
 - Meetings

Work Package Leaders are responsible for the good communication within their WP, specifically with Task Leaders and the Coordination Team. They are also responsible for communicating with the Coordinator as needed, including regular update meetings and reporting.

In fact, for each meeting held as part of the project, the attendance lists are signed, dated and then archived. This is also the case for the minutes, which are crucial for keeping track of the issues at stake in the project and the solutions proposed for advancing its implementation. As regards events, the minutes are published in the 'minutes' folder in the 'General' tab of the Teams group. For WP meetings, the minutes are published in each work package channel in the "Meetings" folder.

Minutes can also be transcribed directly using the 'Automatic Transcription' tool available on Teams. For each meeting, the moderator can select the 'Automatic Transcription' option by entering the main language of the meeting. The meeting is then transcribed live in the form of notes. Once the meeting is finished, the notes are available in the meeting group as a document.

b. Mailing lists

In order to further enable communication between the members of the ECHOES project, several email lists have been created:

- One general email list for all ECHOES project partners,
- One email list for the Steering Committee,
- One email list for each Board,
- One email list for each Work Package.

The email lists are created using Sympa in Renater (groupes.renater.fr), which makes it easy to manage members and keeps an archive of all emails sent.

Sympa (groupes.renater.fr) is a mailing list server that provides access to a mailing list environment. From this page it is possible to choose subscription options, unsubscribe, access archives or manage

lists. With this context, it is recommended to use free or institutional tools. The Coordination team will use Sympa in Renater and its internal tools: File Sender for sharing and storage files or Evento that is useful to organize a meeting.

These email lists allow messages to be sent to all partners subscribed. This facilitates information sharing and ensures smooth communication between the coordinator and the project partners.

Furthermore, communication by email is a key asset at a time when notifications on Teams are multiplying. Members can get lost in the mass of notifications, so this mailing list initiative will be a good alternative to avoid losing essential project information.

c. Video conferences

WP meetings and Task meetings will be held via Teams.

In general, virtual working meetings should be scheduled at least one week in advance, have a set agenda and produce minutes which will allow tracking of actions items. The minutes should be stored in Microsoft Teams in the folder linked to the correct channel, and partners should be informed of where to find them.

Ad hoc virtual meetings should be organized regularly at WP and task levels to:

- Define and refine action plans, discuss progress and assign responsibilities;
- Share ideas, address areas of concern and clarify any questions / doubts.
- Some 'good practices' for virtual working meetings include:
- Sending a meeting invitation with an agenda (or survey in advance to determine the best time),
- Listing any preparatory activities to be undertaken by each participant,
- Nominating the moderator.

After the meeting, the moderator should post a link in the appropriate Microsoft Teams channel to enable the participants to evaluate the content of the minutes. Once validated, the meeting minutes are considered final.

d. Face-to-face meetings

Plenary meetings of the entire project will take place five times throughout the project's lifetime: at the beginning (kick-off meeting), the annual event (each year during the 5-year period) and the final meeting. Smaller face-to-face meetings will be arranged, taking advantage of major events that several partners may attend.

Additional face-to-face meetings will be undertaken on a work package or cross-work package basis, or for other purposes as needed.

General meetings are communicated about at least three months in advance and are co-organised by the coordinator and a host institution.

2. Document sharing and storage

a. Sharepoint

Sharepoint (a Microsoft tool) is well known for storing and sharing files. It allows users to work collectively on a number of files and to save them automatically, enabling efficient and fluid collaboration between the various partners and members of the project. Each channel within a team has its own automatically created file folder. Therefore, it is necessary to open files with Sharepoint or with the office application directly and not with OneDrive.

The creation of documents and files is essential for the successful progress of Work Packages, and therefore to ensure the production of deliverables in an efficient and collaborative manner.

To ensure that documents are easy to use, it is recommended to use Microsoft Word.

To facilitate the sharing of resources and files, deliverables should be saved in the 'Deliverables' file in the General channel. All documents uploaded onto the shared space must follow the naming convention:

- YYYYMMDD_ECHOES_title_of_the_document;
- YYYYMMDD_ECHOES_WPXX_title_of_the_document;
- YYYYMMDD_ECHOES_name_of_the_board_Title_of_the_document

b. Zenodo repository

The deliverables and presentation materials from the ECHOES project are deposited on Zenodo, within the ECCCH community.

3. External communication

All ECHOES communication and dissemination activities should display:

- The European flag, the smaller UKRI logo and, when appropriate, the version with the funding statement. All versions of the logo will be available to download in the WP02 channel: « Communication materials ».
- The following information "ECHOES is a project funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement n.101157364, with the support of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee n.10110142 & n.10110466." shall be added.

The following disclaimer "Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them" shall be added.

Here is the link to the European Commission guidelines:

https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-05/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf

a. Project logo

The ECHOES project logo is the following one:

This logo may only be used according to the rules described in the guide available on the WP02 channel in Teams, "ECHOES-Logo_Guidelines.pdf".

b. Presentation template

The first and last slides of the presentation template are as follows:

c. Website and social media

The ECHOES website is accessible to everyone at this url: <https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/>

In the « Contact us » tab, anyone interested in ECHOES can write to us using the form available.

In order to increase the visibility and impact of the echoes project, LinkedIn and Facebook accounts have been created. It is very important to follow the project on these accounts:

- Facebook: [European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science – ECHOES](#)
- LinkedIn: [ECHOES EU](#)
- Instagram: [ECHOES EU](#)
- Canal U: [ECHOES](#)
- Bluesky: [echoes-eu.bsky.social](#)

If the partners would like to include any relevant information on these communication platforms, please contact claudio.prandoni@ariadne-research-infrastructure.eu, who is in charge of the WP 02 communication and dissemination for the ECHOES project.

Section 4 – Innovation management and Intellectual property

A project such as ECHOES is meant to lead to important innovations – it is, after all, a part of the Innovation action of the Horizon Europe programme. Consequently, the basic rules of result ownership, use, transfer and dissemination have been outlined in the Grant and the Consortium agreements.

1. Ownership of results

The results produced in the context of the project are owned by the partner(s) who produced them. The granting authority does not obtain ownership of any results.

If two or more partners have generated results together which cannot be precisely attributed to one or the other, they are considered joint owners and must agree on the terms of their joint ownership (use, exploitation, etc.).

2. Rights of use of the results

The parties who own results have the right to use and exploit them. Moreover, a partner can also disseminate its results, in accordance with article 17 of the GA.

In addition, the granting authority has the right to use the non-sensitive information provided by the partners to distribute internally and to the public – for this purpose, it has the right to edit, redraft, and translate the results – and can also store and archive it.

3. Transfer of results

Finally, the partners have the right to transfer the ownership of their results as long as this does not affect their obligations in the project.

Section 5 – Data Protection

According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR – Regulation 2016/679), the partners must comply to the following rules:

- The partners may only collect personal data for legal, legitimate and specified purposes,
- The data collected must be processed lawfully, fairly and transparently, for relevant and limited purposes,
- The partners must ensure that the data they keep is accurate and regularly updated if necessary,
- The data must not be kept longer than strictly necessary for the purposes of the processing.

These obligations will most notably apply to the work of the WP2, with the management of the data of website visitors, as well as that of any interested person who reaches out to us via the 'Contact us' page. In addition, the CNRS and/or any other partner who organises an ECHOES event will be held to these standards when it comes to the personal information of the participants.

In any case, a data management plan will be elaborated by Month 6 (Deliverable D1.2), and will provide more precise information on how to manage data within the project.